

Supplementary Materials: Table S1: Alterations in calcitriol concentrations in murine lung tissue and serum in response to inhalations with 1,25(OH)₂-vitamin D₃ or 25(OH)-vitamin D₃ as well as diet with standard or reduced amounts of cholecalciferol. Data are presented as a mean of calcitriol concentration ± SEM.

Research group (number of animals)	Pulmonary concentration of calcitriol [pg/mg]	Serum concentration of calcitriol [pg/ml]	Vitamin D3 content in the diet	25(OH)-vitamin D3		1,25(OH) ₂ -vitamin D3	
				concentration (compound dose per mouse weight)	time of exposure	concentration (compound dose per mouse weight)	time of exposure
Group 1	30.31 ± 0.14	132.24 ± 1.89	0.5 IU/g	-	-	-	-
Group 2	18.20 ± 0.23	98.61 ± 2.74	0.05 IU/g	-	-	-	-
Group 3	3A	30.13 ± 0.14	0.05 IU/g	100 pg/g	30 min./day for 7 days	-	-
	3B	31.21 ± 0.25	0.05 IU/g	250 pg/g	30 min./day for 7 days	-	-
	3C	37.73 ± 0.33	0.05 IU/g	500 pg/g	30 min./day for 7 days	-	-
	3D	38.75 ± 0.34	0.05 IU/g	750 pg/g	30 min./day for 7 days	-	-
	3E	37.90 ± 0.11	0.05 IU/g	1000 pg/g	30 min./day for 7 days	-	-
Group 4	4A	19.76 ± 0.32	0.05 IU/g	-	-	1 pg/g	30 min./day for 7 days
	4B	30.64 ± 0.16	0.05 IU/g	-	-	5 pg/g	30 min./day for 7 days
	4C	33.16 ± 0.20	0.05 IU/g	-	-	10 pg/g	30 min./day for 7 days
	4D	33.52 ± 0.32	0.05 IU/g	-	-	25 pg/g	30 min./day for 7 days
	4E	34.00 ± 0.15	0.05 IU/g	-	-	50 pg/g	30 min./day for 7 days
Group 5	5A	30.29 ± 0.51	0.05 IU/g	100 pg/g	30 min./day for 14 days	-	-
	5B	31.83 ± 0.88	0.05 IU/g	100 pg/g	30 min./day for 28 days	-	-
Group 6	6A	31.08 ± 0.75	0.05 IU/g	-	-	5 pg/g	30 min./day for 14 days
	6B	32.09 ± 0.86	0.05 IU/g	-	-	5 pg/g	30 min./day for 28 days